

Screening for resistance to bacterial blight of rice under rapid generation advance

M. Eunos, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, Bangladesh; H. Ikehashi, National Institute of Agricultural Science, Tsukuba, Japan; and B. S. Vergara and J. Peralta, Plant Physiology Department, International Rice Research Institute

No effective or economical chemical control measures are available so far for bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda and Ishiyama) Dowson, one of the most serious rice diseases in Asia. The use of resistant cultivars seems to be the most efficient and economical control measure.

The feasibility of screening rices resistant to BB in rapid generation

advance (RGA) facilities at IRRI was determined using 43-day-old seedlings of IR28, IR1545-339-2-2, and CH1039.

Two strains of BB — PXO 61 and PXO 86 — were used for inoculation. IR28 is resistant to PXO 61 but susceptible to PXO 86, IR1545-339-2-2 is resistant to both strains, and CH1039 is susceptible to both.

The BB suspension, applied by the clipping technique, contained 10^0 , 10^{-1} , and 10^{-2} cells/ml.

The plants were grown in a shallow box ($55 \times 40 \times 9$ cm) in the RGA facilities. Nitrogen levels were 0, 2, and 4 g ammonium sulfate/week per box from 7 days after germination.

As expected, IR1545-339-2-2 was resistant to all levels of PXO 61 and PXO 86 irrespective of nitrogen levels, while CH1039 showed susceptibility to all concentrations of both strains (see

table). IR28 showed resistance to PXO 61 as expected, but failed to show severe lesion development when inoculated with PXO 86 strain, especially at low nitrogen levels. This could be due to several factors including the depressed growth of the variety.

Irrespective of nitrogen application, lesion development increased with the increased concentration of strains. Strain PXO 61, on the average, showed smaller lesions than did PXO 86. Of all the concentrations, 10^0 cells/ml seemed to be the most effective for lesion development.

The results showed very little delay in flowering as a result of nitrogen level or inoculation by BB. Screening rices resistant to BB seems feasible under RGA. ■

Length of lesions caused by 2 strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* at 3 concentrations of inoculum on 3 rices grown under RGA conditions. IRRI, 1980.

Nitrogen level ^a	Variety or line	PXO 61					PXO 86				
		Av lesion length (cm)				Expected reaction	Av lesion length (cm)				Expected reaction
		10^0	10^{-1}	10^{-2}	Mean		10^0	10^{-1}	10^{-2}	Mean	
0	IR28	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.3	R	2.8	2.9	2.8	2.8	S
	IR1545-339-2-2	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.3	R	1.5	1.2	1.3	1.3	R
	CH1039	14.8	11.6	9.1	11.8	S	13.4	9.6	8.7	10.6	S
	Mean	5.8	4.7	3.8	4.8		5.9	4.6	4.3	4.9	
2	IR28	1.5	1.4	1.2	1.4	R	4.7	4.6	3.5	4.3	S
	IR1545-339-2-2	1.5	1.3	1.3	1.4	R	1.7	1.7	1.4	1.6	R
	CH1039	15.5	16.7	10.3	14.2	S	17.8	18.7	13.8	16.8	S
	Mean	6.2	6.5	4.3	5.7		8.1	8.3	6.2	7.6	
4	IR28	1.7	1.4	1.2	1.4	R	6.0	5.5	4.9	5.5	S
	IR1545-339-2-2	1.4	1.3	1.2	1.3	R	2.3	1.7	1.5	1.8	R
	CH1039	17.5	16.3	16.0	16.6	S	19.2	18.3	17.5	18.3	S
	Mean	6.9	6.3	6.1	6.4		9.2	8.5	8.0	8.5	

^a0, 2, 4 grams ammonium sulfate/box per week.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Screening for brown planthopper resistance

K. Natarajan and K. C. Chandu, Entomology Division, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

Two hundred and four cultivars from AICRIP and IRRI were field-tested for

resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) in a randomized replicated trial at the AICRIP center, Aduthurai, in kuruvai 1978. The planting time was adjusted so that BPH infestation was high at flowering. For each variety 2 rows of 17 hills, 1 seedling/hill, were planted. The susceptible checks TN1 and Jaya were planted as skip rows after every 10 cultivars, and 8 rows of Jaya were

planted 1 month earlier around the test varieties. The border rows of Jaya were sprayed with 0.02% methyl parathion at 10-day intervals to encourage BPH buildup. Estimates of BPH damage were made on 2 dates about 1 week apart during peak BPH infestation; 5 plants/row of each cultivar were evaluated.

No cultivar was immune to BPH attack, but 11 showed some field

Reaction of rice varieties to brown planthopper (BPH) attack at Aduthurai, India.

Cultivar	Source	BPH population (mean no./ seedling)
ARC6564	AICRIP MR5	2.5
ARC6519	AICRIP MR6	3.0
ARC14636	AICRIP BPHS88	3.0
ARC14166-A	AICRIP MR16	2.8
T1426	AICRIP MR3	3.1
Manohar Sali	AICRIP BPHS122	2.9
Parakulaw	AICRIP MR4	2.8
IET6187	AICRIP BPHRVT (Kh '78)	2.7
PTB33	IRRI-IRTP No. 03302	2.0
Hondarawala (Acc. 15634)	IRRI-IRTP No. 04861	2.0
PTB19 (Athikraya) (Acc. 61 07)	IRRI-IRTP No. 01151	1.9
TN1 (susceptible check)		21.4
Java (susceptible check)		122.3

resistance (see table).

Varieties with large space between tillers because shoots grow obliquely from the base had lower BPH populations;

ARC14766-A had 3 BPH/hill of 2 seedlings. Conversely, varieties with compact tillers had the maximum BPH population. ■

Varietal resistance to rice weevil

S. S. Virmani, rice breeder, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko (presently visiting scientist, Plant Breeding Department, International Rice Research Institute); P. K. B. Menon, professor of biology, Cuttington University College, Suakoko; and A. S. Gobeh, research assistant (Entomology), Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko, Bong County, Liberia

The rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* is a

widespread pest of stored grain in the tropics. The pest caused severe damage in the seed store at the Suakoko Experiment Station, where temperature and humidity were not controlled. Some cultivars were consistently more damaged than others in the same storage conditions.

To study varietal differences in rice weevil damage, 500 healthy grains of 18 varieties were infested with 100 insects each under controlled conditions. Damage was recorded as percentage of grains damaged 8-9 weeks after

Varietal differences in damage caused by the rice weevil and hairiness of grain surface. Liberia.

Variety or line	Damage (%)	Grain surface	Weevils (no.) found on 10 panicles before harvest
P14	66.5	Glabrous	—
IRAT10	30.0	"	—
IR937-55-3	31.0	"	—
Juma 1	20.6	"	6
TOS2581	32.1	"	14
TOS4030	25.0	"	—
M4	14.8	Hairy	—
TOS2583	12.1	Glabrous	9
M18	10.0	Hairy	5
IR5	0.6	"	—
Gissi 27	2.0	"	—
Suakoko 8	2.0	"	—
LAC23	0.5	"	—
IR1754-F5B-23	0.7	Glabrous	10
M55	3.9	Hairy	7
IRAT13	2.7	"	8
OS6	1.5	Glabrous	9
63-83	2.4	Hairy	2

infestation. Varietal differences in resistance to the pest were contrasting. P14, IRAT10, IR937-55-3, Juma 1, TOS2581, and TOS4030 were found susceptible; M4, M18, and TOS2583 were moderately susceptible; and IR5, Suakoko 8, Gissi 27, LAC23, M55, OS6, 63-83, IRAT13, and IR1754-F5B-23 were resistant (see table).

Weevils on IR5 and LAC23 were found dead within 2-3 weeks. Seven of the nine resistant varieties had hairy grain surfaces; all susceptible varieties had glabrous grain surfaces; moderately susceptible varieties had either hairy or glabrous grain surfaces.

The resistance mechanism appears to be either morphological or biochemical in nature or both in different varieties.

Pest infestation in the field occurred before harvest. Rice varieties with smooth grain surfaces attracted more weevils than varieties with hairy grain surfaces (see table).

A Hymenopteran parasite and a Heteropteran predator attacked the rice weevil larvae during storage. ■

Assessment of yield losses caused by the earhead-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* Walker

D. J. Pophali, P. D. Deshmukh, U. K. Kaushik, S. K. Shrivastava, G. L. Patidar, and G. A. Gangrade, Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, College of Agriculture, Raipur, Madhya Pradesh, India

The earhead-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is a serious pest of paddy at crop maturity. During the day the pest hides in the dry soil but at night the larvae climb the plant and cut down the rachillae either for food or as a behavioral habit.

Eleven paddy varieties, which are known to be gall midge resistant, were assessed for grain loss by picking up the cut portions of the panicles in three 1- × 1-m² plots (see table). The insect population varied from 12 to 14 larvae/m² at harvest, despite their migration to adjoining unharvested areas. The weight of the cut-down grain in various varieties was assessed against total yield of the fields.